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THE IMPORTANCE OF USING FREE PARENTING TECHNOLOGY IN THE UPBRINGING OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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ANNOTATION

It is well-known that every child is born with pure feelings. Life, the environment, and adults pollute their psyche. It is a very wrong approach to sharply assess children as smart, stupid, moral, obscene, generous, jealous, strong, weak, and each of them is a feeling that exists to some degree in the human mind. For a free parenting system, a child's mind is not a white paper on which to write anything, as promoted in pedagogy. Every healthy child is born with a number of positive emotions, such as truth, beauty, honesty, and justice, and he demonstrates these feelings in his actions throughout his life. The technology of free education is important because it is similar to working in accordance with these natural human qualities and is aimed at improving them. Both in the pre-school system and at the school level, it is desirable that the educational process be based on absolute freedom, in accordance with the natural features, interests and capabilities of the child.

Keywords: Personality, education, free upbringing, freedom, humanism, intellectual freedom.

ВАЖНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ СВОБОДНОЙ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ВОСПИТАНИИ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Известно, что каждый ребенок рождается с чистыми чувствами. Жизнь, окружающая среда и взрослые загрязняют их психику. Очень неправильно резко оценивать детей как умных, глупых, нравственных, непристойных, щедрых, сильных, слабых, и у каждого из них есть чувство, в той или иной мере существующее в сознании человека.

Для свободной системы воспитания ум ребенка – это не белая бумага, на которой можно что-то написать, как это пропагандируется в педагогике. Каждый здоровый ребенок рождается с рядом положительных эмоций, таких как правда, красота, честность, справедливость, и демонстрирует эти чувства в своих поступках на протяжении всей жизни.

Технология бесплатного образования важна тем, что она подобна работе в соответствии с этими естественными человеческими качествами и направлена на их совершенствование. И в дошкольной системе, и на школьном уровне желательно, чтобы образовательный процесс строился на абсолютной свободе, в соответствии с природными особенностями, интересами и возможностями ребенка

Ключевые слова: Личность, образование, свободное воспитание, свобода, гуманизм, интеллектуальная свобода.

МАКТАБГАЧА ТА'ЛИМ YOSHIDAGI BOLALARNI TARBIYALASHDA ERKIN TARBIYA TEXNOLOGIYASIDAN FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ma'lumki, har qanday bola faqat sof tuyg'ular bilan dunyoga keladi. Hayot, muhit va kattalar ularning ruhiyatini kirlantiradi. Bolalarni aqlli, ahmoq, axloqli, odobsiz, saxiy, qizg'anchiq, kuchli, zaif deya keskin baholash o'ta noto'g'ri yondashuv bo'lib, ularning har biri odam tiyatida u yoki bu darajada mavjud bo'lgan hislardir.

Erkin tarbiya tizimi uchun bolaning ko'ngli, tarbiyashunoslik ilmida ilgari surilganidek, istagan narsani yozish mumkin bo'lgan oq qog'oz emas. Har qanday sog'lom bola dunyoga kelishda haqiqat, go'zallik, halollik, adolat singari bir qator ijobiy tuyg'ulari bilan birga tug'iladi va u hayoti davomida bu hislarni faoliyati, xatti-harakatida namoyish etib boradi. Erkin tarbiya texnologiyasi odamdagi mana shu tabiiy sifatlarga uyg'un holda ish ko'rishga monandligi, ularni takomillashtirishga y'naltirilganligi bilan ahamiyatlidir. Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida ham, maktab bosqichida ham ta'lim-tarbiya jarayoni mutlaq erkinlikka asoslanishi, bu jarayon bolalar tiyatiga singdirilgan tabiiy xususiyatlarga, qiziqishlari va imkoniyatlariga monand bo'lishi maqsadga muvofiqdir.

Kalit so'zlar: Shaxs, ta'lim-tarbiya, erkin tarbiya, erkinlik, gumanizm, intellektual erkinlik.

Development of creative technologies aimed at increasing the psychophysiological, intellectual, creative and personal potential of children on a global scale, innovative education focused on the individual in preschool educational institutions Innovative education aimed at increasing the psychophysiological, intellectual, creative and personal potential of children on a global scale Scientific-practical research is being conducted on issues of improving the quality management mechanisms of pre-school education based on the principles of organization of learning environment and strategic management. In these studies, improvement of the information-methodological system of preschool education management, differentiation of quality education services, introduction of information and communication technologies, interactive and problem-based teaching methods into the educational process, professional development of preschool education system employees' special attention is paid to the implementation of effective forms and methods of development and assessment of innovative competence [1].

In accordance with the trends of innovative development in the field of education in the world, special attention is paid to the improvement of the pre-school education system based on competency requirements.

In particular, organization of high-quality educational services aimed at developing independent and creative thinking in children for the sustainable development goals set by UNESCO until 2030 has been noted as an urgent task. International experiences create the need to increase the effectiveness of the pedagogical process in preschool educational institutions, to introduce the basics of STEAM education from an early age, and to differentiate educational services [1, P.2].

The rapid development of economic and political relations in our country is inextricably linked with positive changes in the social thinking of society members. In order to create positive changes in the thinking of people living in society, first of all, there should be radical changes in the education system. After our country gained independence, great attention was paid to the development of the education sector along with the economic and political spheres. Many regulatory documents on education have been adopted. At the heart of these documents is the issue of developing the country's development as a priority, but through this, the issue of every person living in this society living in conditions with all opportunities and being satisfied with their life is the issue [4, P.5].

Freedom is the highest level of moral value that allows an individual to perform actions, based on an understanding of the importance of the subjective position for himself only without external coercion. As a highly developed civilized being, man is essentially defined by what he seeks and the meaning of his existence. That is why he addresses the environment and the events that take place with a position of determining its significance for his life. Because of freedom, a person not only adapts to the reality around him, but also changes it in accordance with the ideas of a better life [6].

Both in the pre-school system and at the school level, it is desirable that the educational process be based on absolute freedom, in accordance with the natural features, interests and capabilities of the child. Both the free pre-school education system and the school will have to reckon with their willingness to accept or not to pass on knowledge to children. In free education technology, it is important to focus the educational process not on educating, but on meeting the need for knowledge. The system of dominating the mind, body, and activities of the pupil, which has not yet left the national educational practice, and which strives to bring him up in all respects, ignores the natural qualities of the child's psyche: the desire for beauty, purity, and sincerity [2, P.4].

In general, the technology of free education in the education system is to give children back their childhood, to preserve the natural qualities given to them by God and to create the necessary conditions for their development. It is not to prepare children for life, but to value life at this stage, not to spend the most precious moments of this stage on what can be given in the future, and to accept childhood and adolescence as a gift of life. To the child: not a man of the future, but a man who lives in the present, free, understandable, acceptable, with the same rights as adults it is an axiom, a basic rule of proponents of free education technology, to look at a partner as

someone who wants to see their current views, their ideas, as a partner who can accept their ideas as realities that can be realized in the future.

Literature review. Research shows that the ideal of advocates of free upbringing was not to restrict or prohibit the development and abilities of the child. In the West, this phenomenon has been reported by M. Monten, M. Montessori, J.J. Russo, L.N. Tolstoy, V.A. Sukhomlinskiy, Sh.A. Amonashvili, K.N. It has been studied by a number of educators, such as Wentzel.

The concept of free upbringing, which is important for the upbringing of children, was one of the central ideas in Socrates' philosophy in the form of self-awareness and self-development. He saw the issue of the freedom of the preschool child in education as a way for the child to understand himself, to awaken and increase his activity. This idea is reflected in Monten's pedagogy. They both considered their preschoolers to be their partners. Socrates: "I have never been a mentor to anyone. But if someone is inclined to talk to me, I will never interfere." The purpose of education, according to Socrates, is to form a person who is both physically and mentally mature. This goal can only be achieved if a preschooler strives for self-improvement.

Michel de Monten, in her book *Experiments*, writes: "It is impossible to draw conclusions based on what others know about the truth".

Maria Montessori's free parenting technology is based on the educator's individual approach to each child. As the French writer Jean-Jacques Rousseau once said, "Man is born perfect, but society cripples him by his upbringing".

Russo suggests not to interfere in the will of the child, not to force him to do anything, not to forget to be firm and demanding towards the foster child, and at the same time not to satisfy any whims. He believes that it is better to direct a person to good deeds of his own free will than to force him to do so.

L. N. Tolstoy emphasizes that the implementation of the content of education and the internal structure of the school on the basis of the wishes of preschool children, the voluntary study of knowledge will give the expected effect. According to him, the child remembers what he wants, as much as he wants. Tolstoy sees the upbringing of a child, the attempt to form in him some moral qualities, as an oppression of the child by adults. In his opinion, upbringing should be in accordance with the moral qualities of the child as much as possible. There is no need for extra stress.

It should be noted that the idea of free education is based on factors such as nature, society and culture. At the center of this trinity is the free individual. When the educational process is based on the principles of free upbringing, the process of communication between the educator and the student, the preschool child and the preschool child is based on equality. The preschool child voluntarily begins to observe the world and man, to study them, to think, compare, evaluate based on his observations, to draw his own conclusions, or rather, the educational process based on free upbringing directs it.

Russian educator KN Ventsel also advocated free education. In his view, moral qualities should be inculcated not by "implanting" in preschool children, but by instilling in the child a voluntary inclination to spiritual qualities.

According to Ventzel, a teacher who relies on the principles of free upbringing will never be nervous, will not be upset by anything, will be able to control his emotions, will believe in himself, will overcome his egocentrism, will be patient with others and their opinions. Learns to control his aggression, evaluates preschool children objectively, reduces fear, anxiety and nervous tension in children.

Research Methodology. What role does education play in shaping freedom, which is one of human moral values? Erich Fromm writes in his book *Avoidance of Freedom*: “From the point of view of social processes, the main task of upbringing is to prepare the individual for the tasks he has to perform in society. That is, upbringing should shape his character in such a way that he approaches the social character. Then, his aspirations meet the requirements of social life.

We are aware that education is a process based on moral, humanistic values, as a result of the interaction of teachers and students as a companion to the purposeful process of human development.

For the purposes of pedagogical theory, it examines education in a variety of aspects.

First, education is a pedagogical component of the socialization process, which involves a goal-oriented action. In particular, it focuses on the integration of man into society, the development of a complex of social roles.

Second, education is focused on the development of the individual, helping him or her to reach the highest level based on his or her personal abilities.

Third, upbringing implies the acquisition of one's own cultural elements that encompass the norms of life. As a result, the process of upbringing leads to the development of the individual. However, not all of these three approaches reflect the freedom that allows humanity to enter the modern world.

Therefore, upbringing should be goal-oriented in order to understand the existence of the child and to build the design of his life. Only in this way can a child be brought up as a free person.

According to J.P. Sparta, “It is not a matter of imagining what a person is like, but of who he is. Man is a creature who strives for the future and lives on the basis of subjective experience”. These are the first principles of existentialism.

The upbringing of a free individual cannot be determined by free upbringing. The main idea of free education is to equip the child with free behavior, to reduce the organization and regulation of his life by others. However, it is also possible to nurture a free individual in the process of organizing his life and regulating it. The important thing is to regulate the manifestation of the "I" that is the basis of its existence.

In the process of parenting, we need to refrain from preparing the child for something or some situation in the future. Because the time from birth to the end of one's life is unique. The life of a child is its present, its meaning must be measured. Every child has the right to live and to understand life independently. They are free to choose their partners for communication and to socialize in the world of adults and peers.

Such a child's free rights do not imply harm to him. Adults need to pay attention to this in their social interactions with children.

But it is also wrong to limit a child to such an extent that he loses his independence and limits his ability to understand his own actions. Research shows that the term "impossible" used by educators and adults to refer to children is more commonly used than "possible." Such strict bans can have a number of consequences. First of all, conformism, which is the basis of the psychology of slavery in the child, leads to the formation of a sense of "pleading" to adults. On the other hand, the often used phrase "impossible" causes a constant negative reaction in the child. As a result, it was found that groups of unruly children in children become involved in criminal activities, and the cause of deviant behavior is the strong desire for freedom to escape various prohibitions.

As we nurture a truly free person, we must not find a solution to his or her problems from childhood. Perhaps the problem situations that arise in the child should be solved together with him, putting his thoughts at a high level. Obstacles and difficulties encountered by the child along the way do not negatively affect his development, but serve as a factor to accelerate this process. According to the scientist LV Vygotsky, "Life puts before the child various obstacles that must be overcome. As each obstacle is overcome, it will continue to rise".

Self-development is when a child implements his or her own project to improve the qualities he or she needs. Every child has their own idea of the ideal they are striving for. Motivational, active and reflexive criteria of readiness for self-development differ. Motivation criteria include the formation of sustainable motivation for self-improvement. This is based on the child's desire to know himself, the need to acquire new competencies, the desire to find the means of self-development.

Performance criteria are reflected in the actual design of the self-development and project implementation. It involves defining the prospects for self-development, knowing the ways to achieve the goals of self-development, and making real efforts to gain new powers.

The reflexive criterion is reflected in the self-assessment of the results of self-development, taking into account the real possibilities, and in the determination of its prospects, which includes the exercise of self-control of change, means analyzing the factors that affect an individual's change, being aware of the consequences of self-improvement.

There are three main stages in shaping children's readiness for self-development: propaedeutic, topical, and reflective.

The propaedeutic phase involves helping children become self-aware, preparing them to project their development. The main tool at this stage is specially designed trainings, individual counseling. At the present stage, the self-development design needs pedagogical encouragement and assistance in project implementation. An effective tool at this stage is stimulus diagnostics.

The analytical phase includes an understanding of the results of self-development by children, an assessment of the use of the opportunities of the sanatorium school, the definition of new tasks of self-development based on the acquisition of new competencies.

In the process of nurturing a free personality, it is very important that the children themselves or their various associations in the humanistic direction become the subject of education. You can become a truly free person not only when you define the prospects of your life, but also when you participate in defining and changing the prospects of your community's activities.

Analysis and results. As noted above, freedom and social responsibility are in a dialectical relationship. He associated the formation of individual responsibility with an understanding of one's own worth. A free man independently makes a social choice that is always a responsible move. Actions consistent with this choice can have irreversible and fateful consequences for themselves and for other citizens and for society as a whole. It is impossible to bring up a free man without forming a sense of duty, obligation, inner discipline.

However, an analysis of social upbringing practices allows us to conclude that, as before, in organizing children's lives, the focus is on shaping executive activity, adhering to social norms to avoid conviction or punishment.

The role of the teacher, the essence of his relationship with children, is of great importance for the upbringing of a free man. Our research has shown that the upbringing of a free man depends on the following conditions:

- the refusal to strictly regulate the lives of students, the need for them to take a step-by-step approach to achieving what is conceived in a rational way with a certain determination. teaching z-self-organization and self-management techniques;
- directing teachers to the inner world - the world of children's experiences, without which it is impossible to establish reliable relationships and deep connections;
- recognition by the teacher of the autonomy of the child's inner world in the practical affirmation of the right of the person to freely express the "I";
- teachers refuse to directly answer the growing questions of the growing person, to solve any problem for him and even with him;
- engage students in a variety of situations that may be an event for them, of personal significance, and that encourage social choice.

Conclusions and Recommendations. Freedom plays the role of the most important moral values of human existence, and the upbringing of a free man reflects the manifestation of this value in pedagogical activity and can be seen as a goal of social education. According to the proponents of free education technology, the development of the child's creative individuality should become the highest goal of education. There is nothing hostile to society and culture in it, on the contrary, the social and cultural principle is more widely recognized in the theory of free education.

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